

Influence of thinning intensity on sexual *versus* vegetative regeneration of *Quercus pubescens* Willd. coppices

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ABSTRACT

Regeneration is a key process to enhance the long-term resilience of Mediterranean forests, particularly in coppices. Coppicing primarily relies on vegetative regeneration through stump sprouting after clearcutting, allowing short intervals between harvests. However, this regeneration pathway is now compromised due to coppice ageing. Thinning, which reduces competition and promotes tree growth, offers potential to enhance sexual regeneration (*i.e.*, seedling establishment), thus genetic diversity. To understand regeneration responses in an old *Quercus pubescens* coppice (70–80 years since last cut), we followed the effects of a thinning gradient (from 0% to 100% harvesting) on sexual and vegetative regeneration in a three-year study. Our results confirm classical silvicultural recommendations for rapid regeneration by sprouting: clearcutting and heavy thinning promote sprouts to establish and grow faster. Maximum stump sprout length reached 70.5 ± 1.5 cm one year after harvest in clear-cut plots, *versus* 47.5 ± 2.1 cm in 25%-thinned plots. However, increasing thinning intensity hindered *Q. pubescens* seedling establishment, likely due to reduced canopy cover creating less favorable microclimatic conditions for germination. On average, three times more new seedlings emerged in the unthinned control plots than in the 75%-thinned plots. In contrast, seedling growth was enhanced by increasing thinning, most probably illustrating the ontogenetic shift in light requirements. Moderate thinning appears to be a compromise strategy for fostering seedling growth after their initial recruitment. However, long-term monitoring is needed to refine thinning prescriptions for optimal *Q. pubescens* regeneration and to fully understand thinning effects on both regeneration pathways.

1. Introduction

The preservation of the structure and functions of Mediterranean forests is a major challenge for forest management. Adaptive solutions that efficiently enhance long-term forest resilience are lacking, in favor of short-term risk reduction and resistance strategies (Vilà-Cabrera et al., 2018).

Adaptive management is all the more important in the Mediterranean basin, where human activities have profoundly altered forest distribution, structure and species composition (Blondel, 2006; Quézel and Barbero, 1990). Among a large number of ecosystem services, wood production through silviculture has been a dominant factor in management decisions (Bottalico et al., 2014; Nocentini et al., 2022; Palahi et al., 2008). This is illustrated by the fact that, in Southern Europe, 75% of forests are designated as "available for wood supply" (FAO, 2000),

highlighting the prevalence of timber exploitation. In the case of Mediterranean broadleaf forests, coppicing is one of the oldest silvicultural practices (Matula et al., 2012). This ancient management method primarily produces firewood and charcoal in particular in evergreen and deciduous oak forests, alongside with other products such as fruits and bark (Hamer, 1995; Nocentini and Coll, 2013). Coppicing primarily relies on vegetative regeneration by stump sprouting after felling (mainly clearcutting), allowing for shorter harvest intervals than high forests regenerated by seeds (Ducrey and Turrel, 1992; Giovannini et al., 1992). Harvest rotations, generally ranging from 15 to 35 years, are tailored to the specific tree species and desired product (Bottalico et al., 2014; Chirici et al., 2020; Spinelli et al., 2016). Mediterranean oak stands represent a large part of the broadleaf forests traditionally managed as coppices (Fabbio, 2016). After World War II, these stands were largely abandoned in favor of other energy sources, especially in

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European countries such as France or Spain (Prévosto et al., 2013; Salomón et al., 2017; Vadell et al., 2022). Nowadays, forest biomass is increasingly considered as a renewable source of energy, and coppicing is widely revived to provide biomass from forests (Santi et al., 2024). However, the reduced sprouting capacity in abandoned and old coppices threatens vegetative regeneration (Ladier et al., 2014; Prévosto et al., 2013).

Furthermore, Mediterranean oak forests are subject to increasing environmental constraints with the ongoing climate change particularly due to more frequent and more intense droughts and heat waves (IPCC, 2023; Lionello et al., 2014, 2008). These climatic events are unfavorable for forest growth and health, causing dieback, defoliation and branch mortality, but also facilitating epidemic development of diseases and parasites (Allen et al., 2015; Lemaire et al., 2022).

Sexual regeneration, or regeneration by seeds, is crucial for adapting forest stands to harsher climatic conditions. Seedlings, which result from genetic recombination, undergo natural selection. This process makes them more likely to produce individuals better adapted to their environment (Bussotti et al., 2015; Vilà-Cabrera et al., 2018).

However, particularly since the beginning of the 21st century in the Mediterranean basin, this regeneration pathway faces substantial challenges (Plieninger et al., 2010; and Tyler et al., 2006 for Californian oaks). Recruitment is lacking, and the young seedlings that do emerge have low survival rates and exhibit a reduced growth (Gauquelin et al., 2016; Prévosto, 2020). Moreover, the regeneration process is subject to several limiting factors. Acorn production is highly variable and predation (e.g., rodents or wild boar) is high (Gómez et al., 2008). Developmental stages are influenced by ecological filters, notably soil properties and microclimatic conditions (e.g., soil moisture or light availability) (Mendoza et al., 2009).

Thinning, which reduces tree density, is known to improve the growth and health status of remaining trees by reducing competition for resources (Kerr and Haufe, 2011). Its effect is particularly noticeable to limit the impact of drought on remaining tree growth (Cabon et al., 2018; Sohn et al., 2016). It is also already recommended for carbon sequestration (Zhang et al., 2018; Mäkipää et al., 2023), biodiversity provision (Li et al., 2020), and fire risk reduction (Taylor et al., 2021). In addition, this management method could be recommended for long-term successful establishment of seedlings as suggested, for example, by Kerr and Haufe (2011). Indeed, thinning is a common practice to boost natural regeneration, mainly by increasing light availability on the forest floor, which favors seedling survival and growth. However, there have been few experiments in Mediterranean oak stands specifically investigating how thinning intensity affects sexual regeneration. This is because striking the right balance is challenging: too little canopy opening (low thinning) can result in insufficient light, while too much reduction (high thinning) can create unfavorable microclimatic conditions or can exacerbate vegetation competition (Retana et al., 1999). In that respect, Prévosto et al. (2013) reported that although initial establishment of *Quercus pubescens* seedlings is possible, their development and long-term survival are compromised in 10–40% thinning plots. Espelta et al. (1995) reported that the *Q. ilex* sapling stage is only reached in stands with sufficient light availability for seedling growth. Moreover, they found that sapling recruitment was hindered in clear-cuts due to a high level of resprouting competition and a lack of acorn sources in the immediate aftermath of harvesting. Consequently, these studies offer no clear silvicultural recommendations, highlighting the need for further research on regeneration across a thinning gradient.

To better understand the two regeneration pathways (vegetative versus sexual), we established a thinning gradient (from 0% to 100% harvesting) in 2022 in a Mediterranean *Q. pubescens* old coppice (70–80 years since last cut). We monitored during three years the establishment and growth of seedlings (originated from acorns) and vegetative shoots (stump and root sprouts). We hypothesized that: 1) thinning intensity positively influences the emergence and growth of new shoots resulting

from vegetative reproduction (Espelta et al., 1999) and 2) thinning intensity negatively affects seedling establishment and survival but positively influences seedling growth (Bran et al., 1990; Retana et al., 1999).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. *Quercus pubescens* vegetative and sexual reproduction

Quercus pubescens Willd. (Fagaceae), or downy oak, is a deciduous oak, native to the Mediterranean basin, commonly found in southern Europe and southwestern Asia, from northern Spain (Pyrenees) to the Crimea and the Caucasus (Ganatsas and Tsakalidimi, 2013). This species is more common on hillsides between 200 and 800 m a.s.l. (Pasta et al., 2016) and is characteristic of the supramediterranean bioclimate (Quezel, 1979). It is well adapted to withstand moderate summer drought stress and low winter temperatures, but sensitive to extreme climatic conditions, such as frequent frost or severe drought events typically found under continental climate (Pasta et al., 2016). It grows on both acidic and calcareous soils in the sub-Mediterranean region, but is predominantly encountered on the latter soil type and behaves as a heliophilous and thermophilous species (Contran et al., 2013; Pasta et al., 2016). In France, downy oak forests, as the main species, cover 1, 413,000 ha (841,000 ha considering forests with *Q. pubescens* covering more than 75% of the canopy) (IGN, 2024). In southeastern France, many stands are old coppice forests due to a decrease in the frequency of coppice cuts in recent decades (Ladier et al., 2014).

In coppices, stems originating from stump sprouts following a previous cut are grouped as stools. More precisely, the term “stool” refers to a cluster of at least two stumps with an underground connection (Pyttel et al., 2013). Determining the coppicing history and age of a stool’s underground structure is challenging.

In this study, we analyzed individual stumps, noting their association with other stumps and/or remaining stems within a stool (Fig. 1). A stem remaining in the stool indicates that not all the stems in the same stool were cut.

Quercus pubescens is capable of both vegetative and sexual regeneration. Here, we will distinguish between two different forms of vegetative strategy: stump sprouts (which grow alongside the recently cut stump from dormant buds along the stem or at the root collar) and root sprouts which originate at various points along the roots (also called “root suckers”) (Fig. 2.).

2.2. Study site

The study was conducted in a forest located in Saint-Christol-d’Albion (SE France, 44°02′58.0″N 5°32′35.8″E, 875 m a.s.l.). An experimental site was established as part of the H2020 HoliSoils project (<https://holisoils.eu>) in a mature *Q. pubescens* coppiced stand (approximate age since last cut: 70–80 years) mixed with a few other species such as *Aria edulis* Willd. and *Torminalis glaberrima* Gand. (Rosaceae), *Castanea sativa* Mill. (Fagaceae), *Juniperus communis* L. and *Pinus sylvestris* L. (Pinaceae). The soil is deep (> 1 m), with silty-clay to clay texture in the deeper layers. The climate is characterized by an average annual precipitation of 980 ± 47 mm and an annual mean temperature of 10.1 ± 1.1 °C (mean ± standard error calculated for the 1995–2024 period with the Saint-Christol-d’Albion climatological station data, Météo-France (2024)), i.e., typical of the supra-mediterranean bioclimate (Table 1) (Quézel and Médail, 2003; Rivas-Martínez et al., 2011).

In March 2022, a forest thinning gradient was established in a 5 ha fenced stand to exclude large herbivores. A pre-thinning tree inventory, including DBH measurements, was carried out to determine initial stand characteristics (density, basal area). Subsequently, five thinning treatments, representing 0% (control), 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% (clear-cut) total basal area removal, were randomly assigned to 40 plots (30 × 15 m), with eight replicates per treatment. Stems for cutting are selected randomly and regardless of species. The thinning was done using

Fig. 1. Vocabulary of the stool.

Fig. 2. Vegetative and sexual reproduction.

Table 1

Climatic conditions of the experimental site. Mean \pm standard error calculated on data from the 1995–2024 period. Notes: $^1I_c = T_{max} - T_{min}$ (T_{max} = Average temperature of hottest month; T_{min} = Average temperature of coldest month); $^2I_c' = I_c + [\text{altitude} * (0.6/100)]$; $^3I_t = (T + M + m) \times 10$ (T: average yearly temperature; M: average highest temperatures of coldest month; m: average lowest temperatures of coldest month).

Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	875 m
Average yearly temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	10.1 ± 1.1
Average yearly precipitation (mm)	980 ± 47
Average temperature of hottest month (T_{max} in $^{\circ}$ C)	19.5 ± 0.2
Average temperature of coldest month (T_{min} in $^{\circ}$ C)	1.5 ± 0.2
Average highest temperatures of coldest month (M in $^{\circ}$ C)	6.9 ± 0.3
Average lowest temperature of coldest month (m)	-3.9 ± 0.3
Simple continentality index ¹ (I_c)	18.0 ± 0.3
Simple continentality index (compensated by altitude) ² (I_c')	23.3 ± 0.3
Thermicity index ³ (I_t)	131.6 ± 5.5

chainsaws and the trees (stems and branches) were carefully removed using skid trails (approximately 3 m wide) outside our plots (see Menival et al., 2025 for further details). Average stand characteristics by thinning treatment are summarized in Table 2: In calculating the basal area presented, the DBH taken into account ranged from 2.2 cm to 76.6 cm for all species combined (the minimum among oak trees was 2.9 cm). Mean \pm standard error DBH for all species combined was 13.6 ± 0.4 cm and among oak trees 14.2 ± 0.1 cm.

Solar radiation was measured during two clear days in July 2023 to assess light transmission in the different treatments. Three Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) detectors (tube of 30 cm length, ©SOLEMS DPAR/LEC1C#) were placed in each plot at 80 cm height along a longitudinal transect. Two detectors were also placed in open conditions, outside the experimental plots (i.e., under full light conditions). Measurements were recorded every minute during 24 h. Light transmittance was computed as the ratio of under canopy light availability at each forest point to light availability in the open (Table 2).

Table 2

Stand characteristics (mean \pm standard error, $n = 8$) according to the cutting treatment: total remaining basal area (BA) in m^2/ha ; Only *Q. pubescens* remaining basal area in m^2/ha ; Total remaining density per ha; *Q. pubescens* remaining density per ha; Light transmittance (PAR domain). Different letters indicate significant differences between treatments (Dunn's post hoc tests after Kruskal Wallis tests with p -value threshold = 0.05).

Treatment	Total BA (m^2/ha)	<i>Q. pubescens</i> BA (m^2/ha)	Total density (/ha)	<i>Q. pubescens</i> density (/ha)	Light transmittance
0 %	41.6 \pm 1.8 (a)	40.4 \pm 1.5 (a)	2147 \pm 136 (a)	1992 \pm 131 (a)	14.4 \pm 1.3 % (a)
25 %	28.1 \pm 1.8 (ab)	27.7 \pm 1.7 (ab)	1894 \pm 132 (ab)	1753 \pm 115 (ab)	19.8 \pm 1.6 % (b)
50 %	15.5 \pm 0.9 (bc)	15.2 \pm 1.3 (bc)	871 \pm 116 (bc)	814 \pm 107 (bc)	41.8 \pm 1.8 % (c)
75 %	8.4 \pm 0.7 (c)	8.3 \pm 0.7 (c)	283 \pm 79 (c)	239 \pm 76 (c)	53.6 \pm 3.3 % (d)
100 %	0.0 \pm 0.0 (d)	0.0 \pm 0.0 (d)	0 \pm 0 (d)	0 \pm 0 (d)	82.8 \pm 1.2 % (e)

2.3. Monitoring of stump sprouts

Immediately after tree cutting, all *Q. pubescens* stumps were labelled and their surface section (cm^2) and cutting height (cm) measured. We also recorded the absence or presence of other stumps in the stool (0/1) and the absence or presence of stems still standing in the stool (0/1) (Fig. 2). At the end of 2022 and 2023 (i.e., 1 or 2 growing seasons after cutting), the absence or presence (0/1) of sprouts was noted for each stump, and the proportion of sprouting stumps was calculated for each plot as the ratio of the number of stumps with sprouts to the total number of stumps in the plot. On each stump, the length of the highest sprout (cm) was measured from the collar to the base of the apical bud. Sprouts damaged by herbivores were excluded from the measurements.

2.4. Monitoring of acorns, seedlings and root sprouts

In November 2022, to characterize the masting intensity and evaluate the effect of treatments on acorn density, the number of acorns in 5 quadrats of 50×50 cm per plot was counted. In clear-cut plots, the number of acorns was considered as negligible due to the absence of trees. The number of acorns/ m^2 in November 2022 was not influenced by the thinning intensity (Kruskal Wallis test, $P > 0.05$) and averaged 47 ± 11 / m^2 (mean \pm standard error). This very abundant production of acorns in autumn 2022 in our experimental site (also observed in the neighboring area), corresponds to a mast year - an event that occurs approximately every 3–5 years for this species in this region (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2012).

Within each plot, 5 permanent monitoring quadrats (1×1 m) were established along a longitudinal transect to monitor seedlings and root sprouts growth. All *Q. pubescens* shoots within each quadrat were individually located and mapped, and their height (cm, from the collar to the apical bud) and density (i.e., number of shoots per m^2) were measured. The origin of each shoot (originated from a sexual or vegetative path) was not distinguished at this step, nor was its age, which is unknown.

In June 2023, new shoots establishing in each quadrat (i.e., number of new shoots per m^2) were mapped, this time distinguishing seedlings (identifiable by the presence of an attached acorn) from root sprouts. In the clear-cut treatment, all new shoots were considered to be root sprouts.

At the end of the growing season, in November 2023, the height of all shoots (cm) in each quadrat was measured. For seedlings already present in 2022, the change in height (delta height) from 2022 to 2023 was calculated. A positive delta indicates growth, and a negative delta dieback (usually because the superior part of the seedling has dried out). Dieback was reported in a binary format: 0 for no dieback and 1 for dieback. For survival analysis, we considered alive seedlings (with or without dieback, coded 1) and dead seedlings (coded 0). In November 2024, the same protocol was carried out for shoots already present in 2022 and for new shoots from 2023.

2.5. Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were performed using the R Studio software (version R 4.3.1, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

2.5.1. Stump sprouting analyses

The effects of thinning intensity (remaining basal area), year, and stump characteristics (stump surface, stump cutting height, and presence of other stumps and stems) were tested on the ability of a stump to sprout and on the sprout maximum length. We used mixed models with the plot as a random variable in the R package lme4 (Bates et al., 2015). Stumps with a surface > 1250 cm^2 or with a cutting height > 28 cm were removed from the dataset to improve model robustness and prevent skewed parameter estimates, as they are considered extreme values of explanatory variables (Supplementary Fig. S1). The initial full models included all previously mentioned variables and all two-way interactions. Continuous predictors (remaining basal area, stump surface and stump cutting height) were standardized (mean = 0, SD = 1). Categorical variables were coded using sum contrasts (contr.sum). Models were reduced stepwise using the drop1 function (lme4 package) in R. Model terms were retained if the residual deviation is reduced significantly, using a Chi-square test for model comparison (Zuur et al., 2009). To avoid excluding potentially important effects, we used a relatively liberal criterion of $p < 0.1$ for inclusion of model terms. We examined the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) to determine the best trade-off between goodness-of-fit and complexity. For each model, we used the r.squaredGLMM function (MuMIn package) (Johnson, 2014; Nakagawa et al., 2017; Nakagawa and Schielzeth, 2013) to extract the marginal R^2 , which includes only fixed effects, and the conditional R^2 , which includes both fixed and random effects. Multicollinearity was assessed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Since all VIF values were < 3 , no strong multicollinearity was detected among predictors in both models (Supplementary Fig. S2).

For the ability of stumps to sprout (i.e., presence/absence of sprouts), we used a binomial Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) and a Type III analysis of deviance with Wald χ^2 to assess the significance of the predictor variables. For the sprout maximum length, we used a Linear Mixed Model (LMM) and type III χ^2 analysis of deviance. The normality of LMM residuals was evaluated through histogram inspection (Supplementary Fig. S3), Shapiro-Wilk test, and Q-Q plot visualization. Model predictions for 2022 and 2023 were plotted as a function of the remaining basal area for different stool conditions (with and without other stumps in the stool \times with and without stems in the stool). To facilitate interpretation, standardized variables were back-transformed to their original scale before plotting. Predictions were made by setting the variables "stump surface" and "stump height" to their mean values. The 95 % confidence intervals for the model predictions were computed using a bootstrap procedure with 1000 iterations. Post-hoc

comparisons between stool conditions were conducted using estimated marginal means (EMMs) with pairwise contrasts adjusted for multiple comparisons.

2.5.2. Initial regeneration analyses

The effect of thinning intensity (remaining basal area) on the number of shoots/m² present in November 2022 was tested using a binomial negative GLM and a type III analysis of variance (ANOVA) with likelihood ratio (LR) tests. For shoots present in November 2022, effects of thinning, year and their interaction on their survival and dieback were evaluated using binomial GLMMs (with plot/quadrat as random variables) and type III analysis of deviance (Wald χ^2). Effects of thinning, year and their interaction on shoots growth was evaluated with a LMM (with $\log(x + 1.4)$ transformation and plot/quadrat as random variables) and type III ANOVA with Satterthwaite's method. The normality of residuals was assessed through histogram inspection (Supplementary Fig. S4), Shapiro-Wilk test, and Q-Q plot visualization. Model predictions were plotted as a function of the remaining basal area for 2022–2023 and 2023–2024 with 95 % confidence intervals computed using a 1000-iteration bootstrap procedure. MuMIn marginal and conditional R^2 are calculated for mixed models.

2.5.3. Regeneration establishment analyses

To evaluate the effect of thinning (from 0 % to 75 %), reproduction path (germination or vegetative) and their interaction on the number of shoots/m² establishing in June 2023, we used a binomial negative GLM and a Type III ANOVA with likelihood ratio (LR) tests. The model fit was evaluated with Nagelkerke's R^2 . To investigate effects of thinning, reproduction path and their interaction on shoots establishing in 2023, survival and dieback, we used binomial models. To investigate the effects of thinning, reproduction path and their interaction on growth of shoots established in 2023, we used linear model (with $\log(x + 0.3)$ transformation and normality of residuals check as previously, Supplementary Fig. S5). We estimated the significance of the effects with Type III Analysis of Deviance (Wald Chi-Square) and calculated R^2 for LM and Nagelkerke's R^2 for GLM. Mixed models were not used for 2023 shoot data due to a lack of replicates per quadrat and plot. Model predictions were plotted as a function of the remaining basal area for vegetative and sexual reproduction and 95 % confidence intervals were computed using the standard errors of the fitted values, calculated as predicted value $\pm 1.96 \times$ standard error.

3. Results

3.1. Stump sprouting capacity and growth

The proportion of sprouting stumps was higher in 2023 than in 2022 (Table 3), rising from 49.5 ± 1.8 % to 56.5 ± 1.5 % (mean \pm standard error). The thinning intensity had a positive effect on the stump sprouting capacity (Table 3); in 2022, the proportion of sprouting

stumps was 55.3 ± 2.7 % in the clear-cut plots compared to 42.0 ± 5.6 % in 25 % thinning plots and in 2023, the proportion of sprouting stumps was 58.8 ± 2.6 % in the clear-cut plots compared to 53.6 ± 5.5 % in 25 % thinning plots (means \pm standard errors). The presence of stems in the stool had a negative impact on the stump sprouting capacity (Table 3). The presence of other stumps in the stool had no direct effect on the stump sprouting capacity, but accentuated the negative effect of the presence of stems in the stool (Fig. 3).

The maximum sprout length was 218.2 % higher in 2023 than in 2022 (Table 4). Sprout growth was positively affected by thinning intensity, and this effect was higher in 2023 compared to 2022 (Table 4, Fig. 4). In 2022, the sprout maximum length was 70.1 ± 1.4 cm in the clear-cut plots compared to 45.2 ± 2.1 cm in 25 % thinning plots and in 2023, the sprout maximum length was 155.0 ± 2.5 cm in the clear-cut plots compared to 101.0 ± 4.5 cm in 25 % thinning plots (means \pm standard errors). The presence of stems in the stool had a negative impact on the maximum shoot length (Table 4, Fig. 4). The presence of other stumps in the stool had no direct effect on sprout growth, but accentuated the negative effect of increasing basal area on sprout growth (Table 4, Fig. 4). The surface of the stump had also a positive effect on sprout growth (Table 4): the larger the stump, the greater the maximum length of the sprouts. However, this effect depended on the year and on the presence of other stumps in the stool (Table 3). The positive impact of a larger stump surface is less marked in the second year of monitoring and was accentuated for a stump in a stool with multiple stumps.

3.2. Establishment of the initial regeneration

The number of shoots/m² in November 2022 (*i.e.*, one growing season after the cut, seedlings and root sprouts are not distinguished) was not influenced by thinning (Fig. 5 A). However, the height growth of these shoots increased with thinning intensity during the two monitored growing seasons (Fig. 5B): we observed an average increase of 8.8 ± 0.2 cm and 10.9 ± 0.3 cm in the clear-cut plots during the 2023 and 2024 growing seasons, while these increases were of 2.3 ± 0.2 and 1.8 ± 0.1 cm in the control plots during the same periods (means \pm standard errors). Shoots survival was not influenced by the thinning treatment (Fig. 5C), but we observed a higher survival rate between 2023 and 2024 than between 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 5C). Finally, we observed a decrease of shoot diebacks with increasing thinning intensity, this effect being more marked during the 2023 growing season than during the 2024 growing season (Fig. 5D).

3.3. Regeneration establishment: influence of origin

In 2023, we categorized new individuals as either seedlings (sexual regeneration) or root sprouts. The number of new shoots in June 2023 decreased with increasing thinning intensity, with both seedlings and root sprouts showing higher frequencies in less thinned plots (Fig. 6A).

Table 3

Results of GLMM binomial model testing for the effects of basal area, stump surface, year, stem(s) presence in the stool, and other stump(s) presence in the stool on the proportion of sprouting stumps. The intercept is set for Year 2022, with no stem and no other stump in the stool.

	Estimate	Std error	χ^2	Df	P-value
(Intercept)	- 0.452	0.068	11.14	1	$1.1e^{-5***}$
Basal area (m ² /ha)	- 0.122	0.060	4.10	1	0.04285*
Stump surface (cm ²)	- 0.181	0.043	0.31	1	0.06314
Year	0.240	0.043	6.09	1	0.00129*
Stem(s) in the stool (no/yes)	- 0.680	0.181	56.45	1	$5.75e^{-14***}$
Other stump(s) in the stool (no/yes)	- 0.023	0.046	73.79	1	0.79462
Stump surface \times Stem(s) in the stool	- 0.157	0.195	2.61	1	0.10606
Year \times Stem(s) in the stool	0.134	0.149	3.21	1	0.07316
Other stump(s) \times Stem(s) in the stool	0.373	0.176	17.99	1	$2.22e^{-5***}$

Model fit: $R_m^2 = 0.10305$; $R_c^2 = 0.12098$.

Fig. 3. Interactive effects of basal area and the presence of stems and other stumps on the proportion of sprouting stumps (Table 3). The predicted values are obtained from the GLMM binomial model with estimated marginal means (EMMs). The plot illustrates the predicted proportion of sprouting stumps (y-axis) at different levels of basal area (x-axis), with separate lines for each condition of tree and stump presence/absence: purple solid line= no stem and no stump; purple dashed line = stem and no stump; green solid line = no stem and stump; green dashed line = stem and stump.

Table 4

Results of LMM model testing for the effects of basal area, stump surface, stump height, year, stems presence in the stool, and stump(s) presence in the stool on the sprout maximum length (cm). The intercept is set for Year 2022, with no stem and no other stump in the stool.

	Estimate	Std error	χ^2	Df	P-value
(Intercept)	90.848	2.544	1585.29	1	< 2.2e ^{-16***}
Basal area (m2/ha)	- 13.833	2.658	27.09	1	1.55e ^{-6***}
Stump surface (cm2)	9.682	1.575	37.80	1	1.21e ^{-9***}
Stump height (cm)	- 3.007	1.513	3.95	1	0.0473*
Year	37.512	1.325	801.52	1	< 2.2e ^{-16***}
Stem(s) in the stool (no/yes)	- 10.442	8.049	6.73	1	0.0096**
Other stump(s) in the stool (no/yes)	1.380	1.609	0.74	1	0.3914
Basal area × Year	- 5.838	1.450	16.22	1	6.18e ^{-5***}
Basal area × Other stump(s) in the stool	- 4.355	1.997	4.76	1	0.0295*
Stump surface × Year	4.643	1.365	11.57	1	0.0007***
Stump surface × Other stump(s) in the stool	- 5.050	1.566	10.41	1	0.0013**

Model fit: $R_m^2 = 0.53391$; $R_c^2 = 0.56369$.

We also observed more seedling establishing than root suckers (Fig. 6A). We found that shoot growth increased with thinning intensity (Fig. 6B) and that root sprouts showed greater growth than seedlings (Fig. 6B). Higher mortality was observed in the most thinned plots, regardless of shoot origin (Fig. 6C). Finally, shoot dieback was independent of thinning intensity, though more frequent in seedlings than in root sprouts (Fig. 6D).

4. Discussion

4.1. Traditional coppicing favors vegetative regeneration

Traditional coppice management, with regular clear-cutting, promotes vegetative regeneration and rapid growth for firewood production (Ducrey and Turrel, 1992; Giovannini et al., 1992). In this study, we investigated a thinning intensity gradient, from clear-cutting to no

Fig. 4. Interactive effects of basal area and the presence of stems and other stumps on the sprout maximum length (Table 4). The predicted values are obtained from the LMM binomial with estimated marginal means (EMMs). The plot illustrates the predicted sprout maximum length (y-axis) at various levels of basal area (x-axis), with separate lines for each condition of stem and stump presence/absence: purple solid line = no stem and no stump; purple dashed line = stem and no stump; green solid line = no stem and stump; green dashed line = stem and stump.

Fig. 5. (A) Effects of basal area on the number of shoots/m² in November 2022. Predicted values are obtained from a GLM negative binomial model with Anova (type II, LR); (B) Interactive effects of basal area and year on shoot growth. Predicted values are obtained from a LMM model with plot/quadrat as random variable (ANOVA type II). (C) Interactive effects of basal area and year on shoot survival. Predicted values are obtained from a GLMM binomial model with plot/quadrat as random variable (ANOVA type II). (D) Interactive effects of basal area and year on shoot dieback. Predicted values are obtained from a GLMM binomial model with plot/quadrat as random variable (ANOVA type II). (A–D) Solid lines represent the predicted probability for each year based on basal area. Dashed lines represent the 95 % confidence interval around the predicted probabilities for each year, obtained by bootstrap (1000 iterations).

thinning, and found a positive correlation between increasing thinning intensity and proportion of sprouting stumps and stump or root sprout growth.

First, we showed a positive effect of thinning intensity on the proportion of sprouting stumps, with the highest rates observed in clear-cut plots. Although we did not directly measure the number of sprouts per stump, this metric, used as a proxy for sprouting capacity in studies, as reported by [Ducrey and Boisserie \(1992\)](#) or by [Espelta et al. \(1999\)](#) in *Q. ilex* stands, supports our findings. However, we observed a strong stool mortality (*i.e.*, no new shoot production during the first 2 years after cutting), reaching more than 40 % in clear-cut plots, significantly exceeding reported rates for other coppice species. For instance, [Ducrey and Turrel \(1992\)](#) observed a stool mortality of 2–14 % in a 30-year-old *Q. ilex* stand in the southern France, while [Giudici and Zingg \(2005\)](#) found an 11 % stool mortality in a 60-year-old *Castanea sativa* stand in southern Switzerland. The advanced age of our 70–80 years since last cut *Q. pubescens* coppice, may contribute to this difference as suggested by [Ladier et al. \(2014\)](#). However, the relatively low mortality reported by [Pyttel et al. \(2013\)](#) in a 90 years since last cut *Q. petraea* stand suggests that factors beyond age likely influence the proportion of sprouting stumps. The time the stand has been under coppice management (data we rarely have access to) could be an important factor for example.

We found that sprout growth increased with thinning intensity. Similar results were reported by [Matula et al. \(2019\)](#) who observed increased sprout growth with increasing distance from the nearest remaining stem for *Q. petraea*, *Tilia cordata*, *Acer campestre* and *Carpinus betulus*. In the same way, [Britez et al. \(2020\)](#) observed that the height of *Q. hemisphaerica* and *Q. nigra* tallest sprouts increased with canopy opening. Increasing radiation (going from 14.4 % light transmittance in control to 82.8 % in clear-cut plots) with increasing thinning intensity

can explain this positive effect due to higher photosynthetic rates in the more thinned plots ([Espelta et al., 1999](#)). In addition, increasing thinning intensity induced reduced competition for water with the remaining stems ([Gracia et al., 1999](#)). Our results reinforce the established practice of clear-cutting in coppice management for achieving vigorous regrowth and maximizing firewood yields ([Ducrey and Boisserie, 1992](#); [Espelta et al., 1999](#)). Our two-year monitoring, which captured a positive influence of thinning intensity on stump sprouts length growth the first year showed an amplified effect in the second year, a trend also reported by [Gardiner and Helmig \(1997\)](#). This suggests that the new sprouts have an easier access to resources thanks to an already developed belowground system. However, this tends to narrow quickly during the regeneration process, with a re-equilibration of the biomass distribution between roots and aerial parts ([Espelta et al., 1999](#)).

Finally, we found that thinning did not influence the number of root sprouts, but positively affected their growth and health, as measured by survival and dieback. This is consistent with [Del Tredici \(2001\)](#) who reported that light is not necessary for the initiation of temperate trees' root sprouts, but is essential for their subsequent growth. The observed reduction in dieback in the most thinned plots further supports the hypothesis that heavy thinning favors vegetative reproduction.

4.2. Sprouting is influenced by stool and stump characteristics

Sprouting capacity and growth are determined by both thinning intensity and stool and stump characteristics. We observed that the presence of other stumps in the stool had a negative effect on sprouting capacity, but not on the sprout growth. This finding is clearly in line with the study of [Pyttel et al. \(2013\)](#), who reported for *Q. petraea* that two stumps sharing the same rootstock (*i.e.*, stumps forming a stool) had

Fig. 6. (A) Interactive effects of basal area and reproduction path on the number of shoots/m² in June 2023. Predicted values are obtained from a GLM negative binomial model with Anova (type II, LR); (B) Interactive effects of basal area and reproduction path on shoot growth. Predicted values are obtained from a LM model (ANOVA type II). (C) Interactive effects of basal area and reproduction path on shoot survival. Predicted values are obtained from a GLM binomial model (Anova type II). (D) Interactive effects of basal area and reproduction path on shoot dieback. Predicted values are obtained from a GLM binomial model (ANOVA type II). (A–D) Solid lines represent the predicted probability for each year based on basal area. Dashed lines represent the 95 % confidence interval around the predicted probabilities for each year.

significantly fewer living re-sprouting points than single growing stumps. Interestingly, the presence of other stumps in the stool has no effect on sprout growth, as also observed by Pyttel et al. (2013).

The presence of stems in the stool has a negative effect on both the sprouting capacity and the sprout growth likely due to a dominant flow of carbohydrates and phytohormones towards the standing trees, limiting resource availability for sprouts. The interconnected root systems observed by Salomón et al. (2016) in old *Q. pyrenaica* coppices support this preferential transfer towards the existing trees at the expense of new sprout development. This highlights the importance of considering competition when managing coppice systems, supporting the well-established principle that thinning improves the growth of the remaining trees (del Campo et al., 2019; Domingo et al., 2020; Retana et al., 1992; Rodríguez-Calcerrada et al., 2011).

Finally, we observed that stump characteristics influenced sprout growth, but not the proportion of sprouting stumps. Higher stump surface, *i.e.*, the parent tree size, was associated with higher sprout maximum length. This observation is consistent with the results of several studies on other woody species (Keyser and Loftis, 2015; Matula et al., 2012, 2019), and non-woody species (Moreira et al., 2012). This suggests that parent tree size is a key predictor of early sprout growth and potential future dominance (Swaim et al., 2016). However, we did not observe an effect of the stump size on the proportion of sprouting stumps, contrasting with the findings of Keyser and Loftis (2015) for several North American oaks (*Q. alba*, *Q. velutina*, *Q. coccinea* and *Q. rubra*) and Matula et al. (2012) for *Q. petraea*. In our case, *Q. pubescens*, like *Q. prinus* (Gould et al., 2011; Keyser and Loftis, 2015) may be a reliable source of vegetative regeneration compared to other oak species in mature forest stands.

In contrast with what has been suggested by Giudici and Zingg

(2005) or particularly in the older literature from the beginning of the 20th century cited by Pyttel et al. (2013), we did not observe any effect of cutting height on proportion of sprouting stumps, as also reported by Dinh et al. (2019), Ducrey and Turrel (1992) or Pyttel et al. (2013). We can assume that a range of 0–30 cm in cutting height is not pronounced enough to cause differences. However, we observed a negative correlation between cutting height and maximum sprout length, which support the classical silvicultural recommendation to cut stumps close to the ground to ensure resprouting (Britez et al., 2020; Giudici and Zingg, 2005).

4.3. Traditional management has a negative effect on the establishment of seedlings but not on their growth

In line with previous research, we found that seedling regeneration is less competitive than stump sprouting following intensive thinning (Retana et al., 1999).

We observed a negative correlation between thinning intensity and seedling establishment, consistent with Bran et al. (1990) who found that the lowest germination rates of *Q. pubescens* and *Q. ilex*, occurred on the most heavily thinned sites. This is likely due to the canopy's role in creating favorable microclimatic conditions for germination (Retana et al., 1999). Indeed, forest cover buffers climatic conditions compared with open areas, resulting in cooler daytime temperatures, warmer nighttime temperatures, and reduced vapor pressure deficit (*e.g.*, Valladares et al., 2016; Prévosto, 2020). Controlled experiments would be necessary to further determine the specific abiotic and biotic drivers of these patterns.

Our initial monitoring suggests a potential negative effect of thinning on survival, although the first year is primarily influenced by seed

reserve (Quero et al., 2007). While seedling establishment benefited from shade, growth was negatively affected, illustrating the ontogenetic shift in light requirements (Kneeshaw et al., 2006; Lusk et al., 2008; Niinemets, 2006). Longer-term monitoring is crucial to confirm this trend, as was seen with *Q. ilex* seedlings that were only able to survive for several years when there was insufficient light in the understory (Retana et al., 1999).

The superior performance of sprouts compared to seedlings relies on the stump root system which provides easier and more efficient access to water and nutrients. Thus, sprouts cope more effectively with periods of hydric stress, which Mediterranean and temperate forests are increasingly experiencing due to the ongoing climate change (Holišová et al., 2016).

5. Conclusions

Our study confirms that sprouts establish and grow much faster than seedlings in the first years after disturbance along the gradient of thinning intensity. However, short-term benefits may not lead to long-term adaptation: regenerating forests mainly through resprouting may compromise their genetic diversity and continuity in the long term. In this context, our study clearly highlights that thinning may offer a strategic approach to promote both vegetative and sexual regeneration.

In the light of our results, clear-cutting and heavy thinning are beneficial to sprouting but significantly limit seedling recruitment, likely due to competition from vigorous sprouts. Moderate thinning appears to be a compromise strategy to promote seedling growth after their initial recruitment under canopy cover. However, long-term monitoring is needed to refine thinning prescriptions for optimal *Q. pubescens* regeneration and to fully understand the effects of thinning intensity on both regeneration pathways.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mathieu Santonja: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Anne Bousquet-Mélou:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Christine Ballini:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Virginie Baldy:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Sylvie Dupouyet:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Bernard Prévosto:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Solène Brasseur:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Data availability

Upon acceptance of this manuscript, the data supporting this article will be available in a public depository such as the Dryad Digital Repository.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.foreco.2025.123063](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2025.123063).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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